

My white"swan" in Dexkonobod

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ANNOTATSIYA

This transcript dexkon the region Kashkadarya Okkishlok promotional bod and b in the centre of villages it about promotional topography.

Key suzlari: maple, observatory, Xisor, Kurikxona,

Access: МЕНИНГ the village of G'im in the white village as is referred to. It Dekhkanabad district owned. Village G'im Туанъ Shan to G'his nest South network G'i is His Jesus to G' the ridge south of -G'arbiy network G'ida is located in bo'become, mainly to G'li of territory. Village G'imiz around the high to G's o'lord is. To G's different different trees: spruce, maple, side G'white, willow, terak, almonds, pistachios, cherries, and the like o'sadi. However this tree's fruit is to the ripening of not taking the time to liq, ya'see G'li considered for the case of the territory of the cool weather because they are not matured. Short, summer, winter, while a long lasts. Such weather also of the trees, the fruit does not allow full ripening.

Village G'imiz 2400 meters at a height of located. It to the south by Chof aqcha to G'i o'lord is, this to G'at the snow in the summer also stand what is. To G'let's most high point Xurosan isit 3749 meters is equal. To G's burning in a many villages located in. These villages one Do'konxona as termed, this village G'uzor River's start in the part is located. Der balm water, snow be melting, and the land under the water to is yin. D balm er water's ko'the pay timei march-June months to g'settings comes. At this time the river was the ko'p the amount of water come in, ya'see this simplest ones is called rural flooding. Sel o'zi brings to the plains and also with a very large amount of stone and sand is laid out.

This river its start irG'a case of ida ro'y gives ya'see each year in may, the 12-day or the other out of the water from the spring of the year began on 13 may. Thus, the earth oG'b the reason for the worko'ladi, start his part of the river from a spring, the spring may be located on the lower side from the firstwhile-tiny buloqchalardan suv started out. Ko may 12-may 13 the fountain of days o'Zidan, started out of the water, the river water of the Juneng will remain to the end of not to go out. So it takes out of the water from the spring of each year. This river, like, out on Friday, on Friday to'xtaydi.

Gissar stateo'b riqxonasigachao'the distance present bizdan is located 16 km away. Qo'riqxonada either a'stay and animals going out o'the protection of simlik have been taken under. Methodology'riqxonada 1983 established in the year composed of 78 thousand hectares of the area make up, qo'H riqxonajesus mountain ridge G'is located in the arbiy.

In nature to become too like I am. One day my dad and me to go for a walk , take out, ya'to G'uzorof the river to the beginning get to go. It there unique which fares pointsG'nest ko'my rdi. Our village is near a place Maydanak loud gustoG' observatoryi located. Maydanak territory, Kashkadarya region, Yakkabog'G' and Kamashi district of the border to go is adjacent to. Maydanak sea level above 2600 meters at a height of located, it 's here mainly of the stars o'z o'from rni o'zgarib to be determined are. Maydanak observatory Osmontarash, Beshnov, Eshonmaydon toG's to close the place is located, this toG's in the snow in the summer also the typeaveoadi.

Temur Amir Temur our grandfather G'ori villageG'imiz from approximately 14 km away is located. My dad o'qitish reason great valor, we are the grandparents about мена ko'p so'zlab gave you and me, our grandfatherng G'ori to too get let go. The caves of the surrounding nature from ko'zini will quvnaydi, G'ornang to Qizildaryoning start irmog'i also there, this River's water is very zilol, white water in the summer is also very cold. Ya'see, it iste'cost to be difficult. Daryoda a variety of different fish are there. G'orga

who back bo'lsa, we have, for each chip, each of different type fruit trees o'sadi. G'orga enter the two locations , there are ya'see ai of the stables, the latter , while 'G'or oG'zi is. G'or Gissar state theo'riqxonasida located, G'of length , approximately 670 m, the height of while 4-5 meters up makes. G'or in the air in the summer cool, winter warm bwill die.

Xin ulom: the conclusion to make that noted, independent O'the republic of uzbekistan in the state of tuG'my births of his such a natureifrom, clean the aircfrom the breath, not able to take, a prosperous country live very much I'm glad. Especially, we are the village with so I'm proud. So peaceful in the country live the main motivator Presidentimiz Shavkat Mirziyoev's reform is.